

1 **Development and characterization of an electrochemical biosensor for creatinine**
2 **detection in human urine based on functional molecularly imprinted polymer**

3 **A. Diouf^{a,b}, S. Motia^{a,b}, N. El Alami El Hassani^b, N. El Bari^b, B. Bouchikhi^{a,*}**

4 ^a Sensor Electronic & Instrumentation Group, Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences, Moulay
5 Ismail University, B.P. 11201, Zitoune, Meknes, Morocco

6 ^b Biotechnology Agroalimentary and Biomedical Analysis Group, Department of Biology, Faculty of
7 Sciences, Moulay Ismail University, B.P. 11201, Zitoune, 50003 Meknes, Morocco

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* Corresponding author :
Postal address : B.P. 11201, Zitoune, Meknes, Morocco
Tel: +212 535 53 88 70; Fax: +212 535 53 68 08
Email: benachir.bouchikhi@gmail.com

10 **Abstract**

11 In this work, sensor based on a new molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) for creatinine (Cre)
12 detection, using screen-printed gold electrodes (Au-SPE), was developed. A carboxylic
13 polyvinyl chloride (PVC-COOH) layer was first deposited on Au-SPE surface. The creatinine
14 molecules were attached to the surface of Au-SPE/PVC-COOH. Afterward, the polymerization
15 of acrylamide and N, N' methylenebisacrylamid filled vacant spaces around them. The
16 subsequent templates removal left binding sites within the polymer which are capable of
17 selectively recognizing creatinine at different concentrations. To test the sensitivity of this
18 Biosensor, the same procedure without creatinine was performed on a gold non-imprinted
19 polymer (Au-SPE/NIP). Their retention and molecular-recognition properties were
20 qualitatively investigated by means of three instrumental techniques: voltammetry (cyclic
21 voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV)), electrochemical impedance
22 spectroscopy (EIS), and UV-Visible spectrophotometry (UV-Vis). The obtained results indicate
23 that the MIP had a specific recognition ability for creatinine, while other structurally related
24 compounds, such as urea or glucose, could not be recognized on the MIP. In addition, the
25 biosensor was tested on volunteers with different creatinine urine levels and seemed a
26 promising tool for screening creatinine in point-of-care. Moreover, Partial Least Squares
27 (PLS) analysis was used to obtain a correlation between the predicted creatinine
28 concentrations from voltammetric measurements and concentrations measured by Jaffe's
29 reaction as a reference method. The EIS and DPV biosensor responses show a limit of detection
30 of 0.016 ng/mL and 0.081 ng/mL, respectively, with a linear range from 0.1 ng/mL to 1 µg/mL.
31 This study provides a promising strategy to fabricate sensor devices based on MIPs with highly
32 selective recognition ability, simplicity of operation, small size and low cost.

33 **Keywords:** Molecular imprinted polymers (MIP), screen-printed gold electrodes, creatinine,
34 biosensor, human urine.

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36 **1. Introduction**

37 The analysis of biological fluids, as blood, skin emanations, feces, saliva or even urine is
38 becoming a common practice to find out particular patient pathologies. One of the most used
39 fluids is urine, a multi-component complex system, from which the chemical composition can
40 be related to several pathologies [1,2]. One of the urine components in concern is creatinine
41 molecule, chemically designated as 2-amino-1-methyl-2-imidazoline-4-one. It can be found in
42 human urine as result of creatine or creatine phosphate metabolism, after muscle contraction.
43 In mammals, creatinine is the end product of creatine metabolism in the skeletal muscles to the
44 release of energy and is removed from the body by renal excretion at a relatively constant rate
45 [3]. The normal levels for creatinine concentrations in urine and blood are ranging from 500 to
46 1500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and from 700 to 1200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively [4]. However, it can be increased in
47 patients with chronic nephritis or renal dysfunction [5]. Therefore, the assessment of creatinine
48 level at this concentration range with specific detection methods is also important. For this
49 purpose, many methodologies have been developed to detect and estimate this important
50 molecule [6]. In addition, numerous techniques have been addressed, most of them, based on
51 Jaffe's reaction in which the active methylene group of creatinine reacts with alkaline sodium
52 picrate to form a colored substance observed by spectrophotometric measurement [7].
53 However, this reaction is not straightforward as it depends on some extent of particular urine
54 composition, and therefore lacks specificity [8,9]. An electrochemical sensor based on
55 creatinine oxidation to detect electrons transferred from H_2O_2 [10-12] was used by Khan and
56 Wernet [10]. But that biosensor had several disadvantages of stability, cross reactivity and
57 sensitivity. Moreover, Lloyd's reagent (aluminum silicate clay) has been performed for a
58 selective absorption of creatinine and to leave the no creatinine chromogens in solution [13].
59 Nevertheless, several other components were also absorbed while using this technique. Other
60 creatinine detection methods include the kinetic method [4], coupled with enzyme assay, and

61 high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Thus, several enzymatic methods have been
62 reported to improve creatinine specificity, but they are time-consuming and rather costly
63 [14,15]. Recently, electrochemical methods based on a combination of enzymatic cascade
64 reactions have been addressed. These methods are cost-effective, complex, time consuming and
65 the enzymes are not always available [16].

66 To overcome these drawbacks, biological recognition agents, such as antibodies,
67 enzymes, and other receptor Molecules have been widely employed, in analytical and
68 diagnostic practices. Although, these agents are highly specific and sensitive, they are labile,
69 expensive, and have low binding sites densities. Hence, there is a significant demand for robust
70 and stable receptor that can mimic bio-recognition elements [17]. Over the last decade, MIP_s
71 have attracted much attention and been introduced as recognition metabolic changes in human
72 urine related to the development of urinary tract infections like bladder, diabetic, prostate and
73 other cancers [18,19]. Therefore, diagnoses of these can be achieved through the measurement
74 of creatinine contents in human urine [20]. These emerging MIP_s, initiated by Polyakov in the
75 1930s [21], are classified as highly promising artificial biomolecular recognition materials
76 mainly thanks to their versatility and functionality to incorporate binding sites for various types
77 of analytes [22-25]. Sensor devices based on MIP_s are known to present high selectivity and
78 sensitivity, inherent stability under drastic conditions, long shelf life and low-cost. Over recent
79 years, MIP_s have reflected the gradual maturation and have attracted from the scientific
80 community [26-35]. They have been regarded as a promising alternative in various research
81 areas, such as chromatography [36-38], biotechnology [39], environmental science [40], food
82 safety [41,42], biomedical sciences [43,44] and sensors design [45].

83 With this maturation, the preparation of creatinine-imprinted polymer has been made
84 not only through using hydrogen-bonding as the main interaction in the complex between
85 functional monomer and creatinine [46], but also using hydrogen-bonding and covalent bonding

86 to form the complex [47]. Generally, molecular recognition bio-elements are coupled with
87 physicochemical transducer devices, which transform the host-analyte interaction into a
88 readable output signal. Among various transduction methodologies, electrochemical methods
89 have been widely investigated because of their potential advantages such as low-cost and small
90 size [48-51].

91 This work proposes a novel creatinine biosensor device based on a MIP_s functionalized
92 electrode system directed to electrochemical transduction. After NIP and selectivity test, the
93 performances of this creatinine-imprinted polymer sensor and its application in human urine
94 for creatinine assessment were explored.

95 **2. Experimental**

96 **2.1 Reagents and solutions**

97 Creatinine (98 %) was purchased from Riedel-de Haen (Seelze, Germany); carboxylic
98 polyvinyl chloride (PVC-COOH), glucose, ethanol, phosphate buffered saline (PBS 0.01M),
99 sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (96 %), picric acid (99 %), 1,4 dioxane (99.8 %) and urea (99.5 %)
100 were from Sigma Aldrich. N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride
101 (EDC), ammonium persulphate (APS), N, N'-methylenebisacrylamid (NNMBA), acrylamide
102 (AAM), N,N,N',N'-Tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED), N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS),
103 potassium ferricyanide $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ and potassium ferrocyanide $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ were all
104 obtained from Fluka. 2-amino-2-hydroxyméthyl-1,3-propanediol (TRIS 0.5 M) was from
105 Panreac quimica. The buffer solutions used in this work were TRIS and PBS. From a stock
106 standard solution of creatinine (1 mg in 1 mL of PBS (pH 7.4)), less concentrated solutions
107 were prepared by accurate dilutions of the previous solution using the same buffer. To ensure
108 the complete dissolution of creatinine in PBS, a vortex and a hotplate stirrer were used. All the
109 less concentrated solutions of the adopted range between 0.1 ng/mL to 1 µg/mL were stocked
110 at 4 °C. For real detection, the urine samples were collected from volunteers students of the

111 Faculty of Sciences-Meknes (Morocco). They were morning midstream urine samples and were
112 collected in polystyrene urine collection bottles. The samples were directly used to

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114 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of Au-SPE/MIP procedures.

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Fig. 2. Polymerization reaction.

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124 avoid their degradation and consequent change in properties. After utilization, they were
 125 stocked at $-4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a freezer.

126 2.2. Preparation of molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) and non-imprinted polymers 127 (NIPs)

128 Before any deposit, the working area of the Au-SPE was washed for three times with
 129 ethanol. A layer of PVC-COOH (11 mg in 1.25 mL of 1,4 dioxane) was cast on the Au-SPE.
 130 To activate the COOH groups, this layer was incubated during one hour and half in an aqueous
 131 solution of 4 mg EDC and 1 mg NHS prepared in 1 mL of water. By thoroughly rinsing with
 132 distilled water, unreacted carbodiimide species were removed. Afterwards, 3.5 μL of a standard
 133 solution (1 mg creatinine in 1 mL PBS buffer at pH 7.4) was deposited on Au-SPE and the
 134 device was incubated for 4 h at $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The Au-SPE was then washed twice with PBS buffer
 135 solution at pH 7.4 to remove unbound creatinine. Then a TRIS solution was deposited for 30
 136 minutes, to block any unbounded COOH groups left on the surface of the electrodes.
 137 Afterwards, distilled water was used to wash the Au-SPE for several times. The polymerization

138 was then carried out by adding 13 mg of APS in a solution containing 11 mg of AAM functional
139 monomer [52] and 71 mg of NNMBA as cross linker [53] in 2 mL of PBS to create polymer
140 matrix around the template [54]. To accelerate the polymerization, 20 μ L of TEMED solution
141 was also added, and the new modified SPE was placed overnight at 4 °C. The analyte was then
142 removed from the polymer layer by incubating in distilled water at room temperature for 15
143 minutes under intensive stirring and with ethanol for 10 minutes. The same procedure was
144 carried out for the sensor regeneration. The Au-SPE/MIP was ready to use after washing it with
145 distilled water. For control, a gold non-imprinted polymer electrode (Au-SPE/NIP) was
146 prepared similarly but without creatinine. The whole preparation steps are shown in Fig. 1.

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148 **Fig. 3.** Schematic of the spectrophotometer and the portable device system used for
149 electrochemical measurements.
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154 **Fig. 4.** Cyclic voltammetry of sequential immobilization steps onto screen-printed electrodes
 155 towards functional molecular imprinting sensor in 5.0 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ (a) Nyquist plots
 156 of sequential immobilization steps onto Au-SPE towards functional molecular imprinting
 157 sensor in 5.0 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ (b).

158 2.3 Polymerization reaction

159 Acrylamide as monomer was used because of its stability and can be made at a wide variety
 160 of concentrations. Moreover, it polymerizes under mild conditions and carry uncharged
 161 functions that establish hydrogen bonds and dipole–dipole interactions with creatinine. Indeed,
 162 the polymerization are starting from the liquid solutions consisting of a mixture of acrylamide
 163 and bis-acrylamide (N, N 'methylene-bis-acrylamide) which react together. Acrylamide
 164 polymerizes in the presence of free radicals typically supplied by ammonium persulfate. Then,
 165 in

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169 **Fig. 5.** Differential pulse voltammograms of different concentrations of creatinine solutions
 170 (a) and Nyquist plots of different concentrations of creatinine solutions (b) in 5.0 mM [Fe (C
 171 N) 6^{3-} and 5.0 mM [Fe (CN) 6^{4-} in PBS buffer at pH 7.4.

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174 **Fig. 6.** Calibration curves of DPV (a) and EIS (b) obtained in 5.0 mM [Fe (CN) 6]³⁻⁴⁻
 175 in PBS buffer at pH 7.4 with different concentrations of creatinine solutions.

176 the presence of TEMED as a catalyst, the added ammonium persulfate is converted into an ion
 177 Sulfate free radical (SO₄⁻) which initiates the acrylamide polymerization. Furthermore,
 178 acrylamide has a double bond between two carbons, which constitutes a privileged target for
 179 the sulfate radical. The result is a free-radical acrylamide molecule. This latter attacks a second
 180 molecule of acrylamide, to give polymers of acrylamide or polyacrylamide, which is a linear
 181 chain. To obtain a reticulated and stable polymer matrix, it becomes necessary to use a cross-
 182 linker. The bis-acrylamide (equivalent to 2 methyl-bonded acrylamide monomers), possessing
 183 two radical attack sites (2 double bonds between carbon atoms), constitutes a crosslinking agent
 184 of choice [55]. In the absence of bis-acrylamide, the acrylamide would polymerize into long
 185 strands (linear polymer). Bis-acrylamide contains two double bonds, which allow the
 186 compound to act as a cross linker between acrylamide chains and this is what gives rise to the

187 formation of pores. Moreover, the functional groups of the monomer link covalently amine
188 groups of added creatinine molecules. [Fig. 2](#) illustrates this polymerization reaction.

189 **2.4. Instrumental analysis**

190 **2.4.1. UV-Vis spectrophotometry analysis**

191 Absorbance measurements were performed using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer. The
192 urine samples were analyzed using ANACHEM instruments UV220 spectrophotometer in the
193 range of 200 nm to 700 nm by using a quartz cell (1 cm path length). For the creatinine
194 measurement, the wavelength was calibrated at 520 nm. The collected human urine samples
195 were chemically analyzed, in the first phase, by using Jaffe’s method following the procedure:
196 first, a solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (1.4 M) and picric acid (0.036 M) were prepared.
197 A standard solution (S_1) was obtained by adding 1 mL of the urine sample in 79 mL of distilled
198 water. A blank solution was prepared by mixing 0.5 mL and 1 mL of NaOH (1.4 M) and picric
199 acid (0.036 M) with 3 mL of distilled water, respectively. It was used to calibrate the
200 spectrophotometer. After 15 minutes, 0.5 mL S (NaOH) and 1 mL S (picric acid) are added in
201 3 mL of S_1 and placed in the spectrophotometer to determine the absorbance value. To get the
202 level of creatinine sample, a linear equation ($Y = 0.3365x + 0.0482$) obtained after synthesized
203 creatinine measurements was used. Thus, for each urine sample, measurements were performed
204 3 times.

205 **2.4.2. Electrochemical measurements**

206 An electrochemical transducer (Potentiostat) interfaced with a computer has been
207 employed to monitor the electrochemical measurements involved in this study. [Fig. 3](#) illustrates
208 an overall view of the system. CV and DPV measurements were performed in a 5 mM solution
209 of $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-/4-}$. For CV, a scan range from -0.4 V to 0.6 V was used with a scan rate of 30
210 mV/s. For DPV, a scan range from -0.1 V to 0.2 V was used with a scan rate of 10 mV/s.

211 The electrochemical measurement setup consisted of a three-electrode system, where a
212 gold electrode (0.19 cm²) was used as a working electrode, a saturated silver electrode as a
213 reference electrode and a gold strip plate (0.54 cm²) as a counter electrode. The impedance
214 analysis was performed with the PalmSens³ impedance analyzer in the frequency range from
215 0.1 Hz to 50 kHz, under a dc potential value of ± 5 V. The impedance of the electrode is
216 determined by applying a sinusoidal potential of small (peak-to-peak) amplitude and measuring
217 the resultant sinusoidal current. The EIS data can be represented by Bode and Nyquist plots
218 [56]. The results of the electrochemical impedance measurements were analyzed based on the
219 best-fitting equivalent circuit analysis using the implemented EIS spectrum analyzer software.

220 **3. Results and discussion**

221 **3.1 Chemical assembly of the molecularly imprinted material**

222 The results of MIP preparation using both methods are represented in Fig. 4. According
223 to voltammetry's signals Fig. 4a, the deposit of creatinine generates a more important current
224 peak relative to that of PVC-COOH. This is probably caused by Hydrogen movement to form
225 NH₂ (tautomerism) in aqueous solution. After the deposition of the polymer, a decrease of
226 current peak is observed again. But after extraction, it becomes more important than the
227 previous. This is explained by the formation of free sites that allow the movement of electrons.
228 The plots obtained by EIS method are shown in Fig. 3b in which a significant increase of
229 charge-transfer resistances is remarked after the different stages of the elaboration of the MIP.
230 This reveals some modifications in the surface of the electrode which is due to a filled
231 increasing of the free sites. Consequently, subsequent immobilization led to a further resistance
232 increase due to the lower conductivity of the resulting surface. But after extraction stage, this
233 resistance decreases because of the creation of free sites.

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237 **Fig. 7.** Differential pulse voltammetry of sequential immobilization of different concentrations
 238 towards non-imprinting polymer sensor in 5.0 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-4-}$ (a) Nyquist plots of
 239 sequential immobilization of different concentrations towards non-imprinting polymer sensor
 240 in 5.0 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-4-}$ (b).

241 3.2. MIP and NIP sensor responses

242 The binding of the template to the imprinted creatinine and non-imprinted polymers was
 243 studied employing DPV and EIS characterization techniques. The obtained results during the
 244 MIP test are shown in Fig. 5. According to differential pulse voltammograms of the Fig. 5a, the
 245 current peaks decrease gradually with an increase of creatinine concentrations. DPV curves
 246 indicate the movement of electrons through the polymer sites. The current peak decrease can
 247 be explained by an increasing filling of MIP free sites for each increase of creatinine
 248 concentration. In Fig. 5b, the Nyquist plots inform about the interfacial charge-transfer
 249 impedances (R_{ct}) of the electrode which were determined from the diameter of the semi-circle.
 250 It was found that the charge-transfer impedance of the electrode increased by the addition of
 251 creatinine and increased further with increasing concentrations. With higher concentrations of
 252 creatinine, surface modification electrodes becomes more important due to electron promotion.

253 Calibration curves were presented in Fig. 6a, as relative variation of current density (I_0-I)/ I_0
 254 versus Log (concentration of creatinine in $\mu\text{g/mL}$). In the range of [0.1 ng/mL; 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$], good
 255 linearity of the

256 **Table 1.** Comparison of performance of various electrochemical biosensor employing MIP with the
 257 current MIP creatinine sensor.

Detection methods	Linear range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Limit of detection (ng/mL)	References
capacitive	0 ; 67.87	1130	[16]
DPCSV*	0.0025 ; 84.0	2.5	[56]
SqWV*	41.8 ; 407	972	[58]
EIS	0.020 ; 0.67	20	[20]
EIS	0.05 ; 2	40	[26]
DPV and EIS	10^{-5} ; 1	0.016	Current Work

258 DPCSV: Difference Pulse Cathodic Stripping Voltammetry
 259 SqWV: Square Wave Voltammetry

260 calibration plot was obtained with a correlation coefficient of 0.98 for DPV. The same
 261 correlation coefficient value was obtained for EIS technique in Fig. 6b where $(R_0-R)/R_0$ versus
 262 Log (concentration of creatinine in $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was represented.

263 A non-imprinted polymer (NIP) test based Au-electrodes has been also studied for
 264 control experiments in the absence of creatinine. DPV technique of Fig. 7a shows overlay
 265 voltammograms for each characterization step due to a non-existence of binding sites to be
 266 occupied. Therefore, a same electronic flow is ascertainable for each concentration of the range.
 267 Whereas Nyquist plots of creatinine Fig. 7b show simply linear plot with no semicircular
 268 pattern, relevant to an interfacial charge-transfer resistance, and this observation suggest that
 269 only a diffusion-controlled process occurs at the electrode.

270 All tests were performed several times, for days, to check the repeatability and
 271 reproducibility of the biosensor. Then, an average standard

272 **Fig. 8.** Biosensor responses for interfering molecules.

273 **Fig. 9.** The effect of polymerization time on MIP sensor response to creatinine.

274 deviation of around 1 % and relative standard deviation (RSD) < 4 % in a linear range of [0.1
275 ng/mL to 1 µg/mL] was obtained, demonstrating an excellent accuracy of the electrochemical
276 measurements and indicating that the proposed method for the sensor preparation was reliable
277 and reproducible. Finally, results of the NIP test have well confirmed the MIP's responses.
278 Further, the obtained results were found to be reproducible in three independent experiments
279 and the magnitude of curves and R_{ct} changes are negligible. Thus, with DPV method, the
280 biosensor displayed a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.081 ng/mL. In the case of EIS method, a
281 LOD of 0.016 ng/mL was found. Indeed, the performed biosensor is easy to fabricate, reusable
282 after 3 months and highly sensitive compared to those seen in related studies. [Table 1](#) illustrates
283 a comparison between its performances and some reported works'. The low detection limit
284 reported in these investigations ranges from about 2 ng/mL to as high as 972 ng/mL. Compared
285 with related works for creatinine detection [[51](#), [57-64](#)], the current biosensor displays a low and
286 highly significant LOD.

287 **3.3. Selectivity study**

288 To investigate interferences, due to possible reactive compounds coexisting in
289 physiological samples, urea and glucose were used to test the selectivity of the creatinine-
290 imprinted polymer [[65,48](#)]. [Fig. 8](#) indicates the differences observed for these three analytes
291 using the same polymer. DPV curves present little variations of their amplitudes whereas
292 Nyquist plots of the interferers show negligible change of transfer

293

Fig. 10. The effect of elution time on MIP sensor response to creatinine.

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Fig. 11. The effect of incubation time on MIP sensor response to creatinine.

295 charge. It certainly means that the fabricated MIP_s sensor surface show no response to the
296 presence of urea and glucose. All these observations suggest concluding clearly that the
297 recognition (binding) sites of MIP_s are specific to creatinine.

298 3.4. Optimization of some experimental MIP sensor parameters

299 In the aim of improving the biosensor performances, some parameters have been
300 optimized. The polymer solution was deposited onto the Au-SPE with an overnight incubation
301 time. Firstly, this duration was optimized by using 3, 4, 5, 6 h as incubation times. The results
302 in Fig. 9 showed that the optimal signal is obtained for 5 h. Less durations presented no greater
303 current peaks.

304 In following, an elution stage started by using ethanol and distilled water. This deposit
305 (washing) took first 45 minutes. Secondly, duration of the extraction was studied for 15, 20, 25,
306 30 and 35 minutes. An optimal extraction time was obtained for 25 minutes in which the signal
307 remains constant while the increasing durations (Fig. 10).

308 Thirdly, by taking 10, 15, 25, 30, 40 and 45 minutes the incubation time of a creatinine
309 concentration has been investigated. As seen in Fig. 11, an optimal time was found for 30
310 minutes.

311 **3.5 Application of the MIP sensor for the determination of creatinine levels in human** 312 **urine samples**

313 Analytical applicability of the present method was assessed by applying the present
314 biosensor to the determination of creatinine in human urine samples of a group of healthy people
315 with different creatinine levels. Considering that, the clinical range in urine sample (500-1500
316 µg/mL) [66] and the determination range of the present biosensor (0.1 ng/mL- 1 µg/mL) the
317 developed sensor could be applied in urine samples. Indeed, after the step of developing the
318 creatinine sensor, its biological application was then explored. Different biological urine
319 samples were collected in polystyren bottles, put in freezer, diluted in PBS and shake before

320 analysis. A classification study of the different samples was previously done using Jaffe's
321 method by UV-Vis. Therefore, three types of samples were used: Two urine samples with low,
322 medium and high creatinine levels were tested by using the developed biosensor in order to
323 measure creatinine levels.

324 Fig. 12 shows the results obtained by voltammetry and electrochemical impedance
325 methods measurement performed on one urine sample of volunteer (P122) having a high
326 creatine level by taking into account the value obtained by UV-Vis. For each sample, the
327 quantifying test is

328 **Fig. 12.** DPV of one urine creatinine sample (a) Nyquist plot of one urine creatinine
329 sample (b).

330 done repeatedly to take the average of creatinine concentration value. Regarding the values
331 obtained by EIS, a best fitting was necessary by using EIS spectrum analyzer software.
332 Obtained R_{ct} values allowed determining the creatinine level. For DPV and EIS methods, the
333 amounts of creatinine in the human urine samples were determined by the calibration curves of

334 the Fig. 6. Creatinine levels in urine samples found using DPV and EIS methods agree with
 335 those obtained by the spectrophotometer (Table 2). This presented method for creatinine human
 336 urine assessments described averages RSD of 5 % for DPV and 11 % for EIS techniques with
 337 a recovery limit of 96 % and 105 %, respectively. That revealed a satisfactory measurements
 338 precision and trueness.

339 Fig. 13 describes the results of partial least square (PLS) regression model for human
 340 urine creatinine concentrations prediction. In this

341 **Table 2.** MIP sensor results for reproducibility of creatinine urine measurements.

Code	High creatinine levels		Medium creatinine levels		Low creatinine levels	
	P88	P122	P128	P77	P99	P118
Spectrophotometer (10 ³ µg/mL)	2.703	2.975	1.074	1.662	0.780	0.599
	2.748	3.054	1.142	1.685	0.791	0.554
	2.760	3.099	1.346	1.7872	0.803	0.576
DPV (10 ³ µg /mL)	2.668	2.975	0.974	1.705	0.565	0.498
	2.670	2.990	1.030	1.800	0.650	0.510
	2.720	2.980	1.200	1.740	0.700	0.580
RSD (%) (n=3)	0.890	0.250	8.900	2.200	8.730	6.830
Recovery (%)	98.7	100.8	99.6	105.2	82.0	88.4
EIS (10 ³ µg/mL)	2.670	2.850	1.090	1.300	1.010	0.600
	2.700	2.910	1.730	1.900	0.590	0.540
	2.730	2.880	1.100	1.870	1.020	0.570
RSD (%) (n=3)	0.900	1.040	22.900	16.330	22.900	4.290
Recovery (%)	99.8	96.8	121.9	102.2	111.5	95.1

342

343 case, PLS model was built by using all data without separating it neither in training nor
344 validation matrix. One latent variable and a leave one out cross-validation technique have been
345 used to build this model. Fig. 13a-b illustrates DPV and EIS versus creatinine levels determined
346 by Jaffe's method, respectively. A good linearity of the calibration plots was obtained in both
347 cases with a correlation coefficient of 0.99. From the above reported results, the possibility of
348 the biosensor to monitor urinary creatinine content seems to be the most remarkable result.

349 **4. Conclusion**

350 In this work, two main strategies regarding the development of synthetic receptors based
351 on molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) and their applications for real creatinine detection
352 in human urine samples were presented. The combination of three different instrumental
353 techniques, cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV), electrochemical
354 impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and UV-Visible spectrophotometry (UV-Vis), has been revealed
355 as a useful tool for sequential characterization of creatinine immobilization steps onto screen
356 printed gold electrodes towards functional molecular imprinting sensor. The MIPs
357 demonstrated specific recognition and sensitive detection ability for molecular recognition of
358 creatinine in human urine. In addition, urine creatinine levels deduced from the practicability
359 of the developed biosensor were all proved satisfactory when compared to those measured by
360 Jaffe's method, demonstrating the good accuracy and potential applicability of the developed
361 Au-SPE/MIP. Moreover, the limit of detection was found to be 0.016 ng/mL and 0.081 ng/mL,
362 measured respectively for DPV and EIS methods, with a linear range from 0.1 ng/mL to 1
363 µg/mL. This study has confirmed the proposed electrochemical MIP sensor as simple, robust,
364 rapid, non-invasive, portable and low-cost alternative tool for clinical applications of urinary
365 creatinine.

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367

368 **Fig. 13.** Results of PLS prediction of human urine creatinine levels by means of DPV
 369 (a) and EIS (b) methods versus Jaffe's method.

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